

Proposal for an improved Great Circle Reduction formula

L Lindegren (1983 May 26)

Lund Observatory
Box 1107
S-22104 LUND, Sweden

1. Introduction

The HIPPARCOS System Requirements contain a prescription for converting rms field coordinate errors (σ_{η}) into rms errors on the star abscissae on a great circle scan (σ_{α}), the so-called SDR formula, Eqns (1) - (3) below. Careful examination of this formula and of extensive numerical simulations performed by MATRA/LOGICA, the Geodetic Institute in Copenhagen, and myself, leads to the conclusion that a vastly improved formula can now be put forward. The proposed formula is

$$\sigma_{\alpha i}^2 = 1.17 \left\{ (N/M)A^2 + 1.10 \left(\sum_{j \in i} \sigma_{\eta j}^{-2} \right)^{-1} \right\} \quad (42)$$

with

$$A = 1.57 \left(\frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \sigma_{\eta j}^{0.5} \right)^2 \quad (42a)$$

Here $\sigma_{\alpha i}$ is the rms abscissa error for the i :th star ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) and $\sigma_{\eta j}$ the rms error of the j :th measurement ($j = 1, 2, \dots, M$); N and M are the number of stars and measurements, respectively, in the great-circle scan. The symbol $j \in i$ in (42) means that the sum in that equation is taken only over the measurements (j) concerned with star no. i .

Table 0. Comparison of abscissa rms errors according to (42), the SDR formula, and MATRA's accuracy assessments. Assumptions as in ESA-HIP-01624.

B	SDR	'Current'	'Basic'	(42)
9	7.14 mas	5.62 mas	5.69 mas	5.93 mas
12	13.20	12.44	10.83	12.02

2. The SDR Formula

This is an attempt to reconstruct the derivation of the GCR formula as given in the System Requirements (6.1.2.2.1, 15 Oct 1982), viz.

$$\sigma_{\alpha i}^2 = 1.45 (N/M) \langle \sigma_{\eta}^2 \rangle (1.77 + 1/w_i) \quad (1)$$

Here $\sigma_{\alpha i}$ is the rms abscissa error for star number $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, N is the total number of stars in the great-circle scan, M the total number of measurements (numbered $j = 1, 2, \dots, M$),

$$\langle \sigma_{\eta}^2 \rangle = (1/M) \sum_{j=1}^M \sigma_{\eta j}^2 \quad (2)$$

the average variance of the measurements (having rms errors $\sigma_{\eta j}$), and

$$w_i = (N/M) \langle \sigma_{\eta}^2 \rangle \sum_{j \in i} \sigma_{\eta j}^{-2} \quad (3)$$

is the relative weight of measurements on star i . (The symbol $j \in i$ means that the summation is restricted to measurements (j) concerned with star i).
With

$$n = M/N \quad (4)$$

denoting the average number of measurements per star, the SDR formula is more concisely

$$\sigma_{\alpha i}^2 = 1.45 \left[\frac{1.77}{n} \langle \sigma_{\eta}^2 \rangle + \left(\sum_{j \in i} \sigma_{\eta j}^{-2} \right)^{-1} \right] \quad (5)$$

In these equations I have added the star subscript (i) to emphasize that they give a prescription for how the abscissa error varies with the various factors relevant to a specific star, such as its magnitude, time allocation, and number of measurements (n_i). Note that the operator $\langle \rangle$ here indicates the arithmetic mean, according to (2), and not the harmonic mean for which it is sometimes used in the LOGICA report.

The first versions of what would become the SDR formula were derived from Eqn (3.8.15) of the ESTEC Report PF616 (5 Dec 1979, p. 88):

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^2(B) = \frac{UN}{2M_a} \sigma_a^2(B) \quad (6)$$

(neglecting the small terms due to chromaticity and basic angle variations, and making the magnitude dependence explicit). Here M_a is the number of angle measurements between pairs of stars and $\sigma_a(B)$ is the rms error of such an angle measurement. At the time of that report, the frame concept with cyclic observation of all visible programme stars had not yet emerged: the observations consisted entirely of frames with exactly two stars each, but of variable length. Naturally the rms error of a pair measurement depends on the magnitudes of both stars (B and B'); but according to PF616 we may form an average over all the different pairs containing a star of magnitude B as one component,

$$\sigma_a(B) = (1/N) \sum_{B'} N(B') \sigma_a(B, B') \quad (7)$$

to be used in (6). It is interesting that the arithmetic mean of the rms errors was used in PF616, rather than a harmonic or arithmetic mean of the variances, which would appear more 'physical'. This was done entirely on the feeling that a harmonic mean variance would put too much emphasis on the bright stars, and an arithmetic mean too much on the faint stars. It was perhaps also guided by the observation that, as it turned out in Table 3.8.4 (p. 89 of PF616),

$$\sigma_a(B) \approx \sigma_a(B, \bar{B}) \quad (8)$$

for some fixed average magnitude $\bar{B} \approx 9.4$, which looks very plausible.

The numerical factor U was given as 1.7 in PF616, but without reference (except to 'numerical experiments'). The source for this number was in fact my note from 1977 April 15, 'Estimation of the variance V in (A2.1)' (annexed). This describes numerical simulations of Step 1 using random star positions with average density 1 deg^{-2} , eight consecutive great-circle scans with 0.28 deg precession per scan, FOV 0.9×1.2 or 1.4 deg^2 , equal σ_a on all pairs, and solving for abscissae and six instrument parameters.

The main results of four simulations are summarized in Table 1 below. The last column gives

$$U = (2M_a/N) \sigma_\alpha^2 / \sigma_a^2 \quad (9)$$

where σ_α^2 is the sample variance of the abscissa solution.

Table 1. Results of Step 1 simulations by Lindegren (1977 April 15)

γ	ϕ_ℓ	N	M_a	$\sigma_\alpha^2 / \sigma_a^2$	U
60°	1.2°	765	7904	0.285	5.89
63	1.2	765	7834	0.0829	1.70
63	1.4	765	9097	0.0690	1.64
64	1.2	765	7879	0.0813	1.67

From this meagre material, a better guess for the actual field length ($\phi_\ell = 0.9$ deg) might be $U = 1.8$, which however would be more than compensated by the higher star density of the real mission (2.42 deg^{-2}). In effect, $U = 1.7$ was thought to be rather conservative.

In order to apply Eqn (6) to the new frame concept, using absolute measurements of the field coordinate η , each pair was at first simply regarded as a combination of two independent and equal η -measurements:

$$\sigma_a^2 = 2\sigma_\eta^2, \quad M_a = \frac{1}{2}M \quad (10)$$

so that (6) became, with $U = 1.7$,

$$\sigma_\alpha^2 = 3.4 (N/M) \sigma_\eta^2 \quad (11)$$

In view of the uncertainties involved, a margin factor of $4/3.4 = 1.176$ on the variance was effectively applied, in that (11) was modified to

$$\sigma_\alpha^2 = 4(N/M) \sigma_\eta^2 \quad (12)$$

In order to get the abscissa accuracy as function of magnitude (B), a further modification was required. The form of that was naturally suggested by writing, in (8),

$$\sigma_a^2(B, \bar{B}) = \sigma_{\eta}^2(\bar{B}) + \sigma_{\eta}^2(B) \quad (13)$$

so that (12) would become

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^2(B) = 2(N/M) \left[\sigma_{\eta}^2(\bar{B}) + \sigma_{\eta}^2(B) \right] \quad (14)$$

or, more generally,

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^2(B) = (N/M) \left[b \langle \sigma_{\eta}^2 \rangle + c \sigma_{\eta}^2(B) \right] \quad (15)$$

where b, c are numerical 'constants' to be determined.

At this point reference was made to small-scale (50 stars) numerical experiments by Lindegren and Söderhjelm ('How much weight can be gained on high-priority stars?', 1980 Dec 2) and to the theoretical GCR analysis by Høyer et al. [Astron. Astrophys. 101, 228 (1981)]. The first note indicated that the coefficient c in (15) is not significantly different from unity. The second paper showed that, for a regular star distribution with constant $\sigma_{\eta j}$,

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^2 = V(N/M) \sigma_{\eta}^2 \quad (16)$$

with

$$V \simeq 1 + \frac{1}{2} N^{0.333} / (m-1) \simeq 2.77 \quad (17)$$

for $N = 785$, $m = 3.6$ (the mean number of stars in the FOV reduced by the frame overlap factor $\simeq 0.9$). Combining these two results in the form of (15), interpreting the variances in (16) as arithmetic means, we get $c = 1$ and $b = V-1$, or

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^2(B) = (N/M) \left[1.77 \langle \sigma_{\eta}^2 \rangle + \sigma_{\eta}^2(B) \right] \quad (18)$$

Comparing with the magnitude-independent form (12) derived from PF616, it is seen that (18) is, on the average, a factor $4/2.77 = 1.444$ smaller. In order to bring the new form (18) into general agreement with the previous form (which I think occurred in a draft version of the ITT), it was then modified to

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^2(B) = 1.45(N/M) \left[1.77 \langle \sigma_{\eta}^2 \rangle + \sigma_{\eta}^2(B) \right] \quad (19)$$

Recognizing that the different measurements of one and the same star should combine by weight (an assumption supported by the simulations of 1980 Dec 2), the term $(N/M)\sigma_{\eta}^2(B)$ was properly replaced by the inverse sum of measurement weights, leading to the SDR formula (5).

To summarize the various steps and assumptions leading up to the SDR formula, they seem to be as follows:

- A. The factor $U = 1.7$ in (6) originated from numerical simulations (1977) with random star distributions but constant σ_{η_j} (same for all measurements).
- B. When transforming to (12), which effectively also assumes constant σ_{η_j} , a margin factor of 1.176 was applied on the abscissa variance.
- C. To incorporate a magnitude dependence, the formula was split in a constant term and a variable term proportional to the measurement variance at the respective magnitude. The apportionment between the two terms in (15) was taken to be $b/c = V-1 = 1.77$ from the rigidity factor of a regular star distribution.
- D. The factor 1.45 in (19) was applied in order to reconcile it with the magnitude independent expression (12), assuming that the latter holds also when σ_{α}^2 and σ_{η}^2 are interpreted as averages over the stars and measurements.
- E. Finally $n/\sigma_{\eta}^2(B)$ in (19) was replaced by $\sum_{j \in i} \sigma_{\eta_j}^{-2}$, i.e. the weight-sum of individual measurement.

3. Comparison of simulation results: Average accuracy

In this Section I compare the average GCR relations between input (η) and output (α) errors, i.e. without regard to their actual distribution versus magnitude. For this purpose, data for all 'realistic' simulations known to me have been collected in Tables 2 - 9. By 'realistic' I mean that they should involve at least of the order of 800 stars with random distribution in abscissa. The ten simulations (many of which are means of several runs) are:

- #1. LOGICA E26-HIP-00166 run 9 (p. 175). 600 stars with fixed $B = 9$
- #2. LOGICA E26-HIP-00166 run 10 (p. 175). 800 stars with fixed $B = 9$
- #3. LOGICA E26-HIP-00166 Table 3.2.2.1 (p. 189)
800 stars with flat magnitude distribution from $B = 5$ to 12
- #4. LOGICA E26-HIP-00166 Table 3.2.2.2 (p. 190)
785 stars with realistic B-distribution; $\sigma_{\eta}^{-2} \propto (\text{intensity})^{\frac{1}{2}}$
- #5. LOGICA E26-HIP-00166 Table 3.2.2.3 (p. 191)
Same as #4 but with $\sigma_{\eta}^{-2} \propto (\text{mission observing time})$
- #6. MATRA E21-HIP-00767 Fig. 3.2.4/1 (p. 125)
785 stars with realistic B-distribution; weighting not specified
- #7. MATRA E21-HIP-00767 (pp. 180 and 192)
Part of MATRA's 'Basic Accuracy' assessment. Actually, only the number $(V-1)\langle\sigma_{\eta}^2\rangle = 370 \text{ mas}^2$ is given as a result of various GCRs; with $\sigma_{\eta}^2(B)$ from their Fig. 3.3.3/12 (p. 183) and $n = 14.88$ this gives the abscissa errors in Table 7.
- #8. Lindegren (1977 April 15), cf. Table 1. Fixed B
- #9. Copenhagen GI set M-4 (Petersen, Byrnak and Poder, 1982 Aug 7)
From the analysis in NDAC/LO/017
- #10. Copenhagen GI set M-11
Analysed by Lindegren (1983 March 28)

Table 2. Simulations with constant σ_0 and random star positions

#	Reference	N	m	σ_0	σ_α	H
#1	LOGICA E26-HIP-00166 run 9, p. 175	600	4	1.386	2.639	1.904
#2	LOGICA E26-HIP-00166 run 10, p. 175	800	4	1.613	3.115	1.931
#8	Lindegren, 1977 April 15 (3 runs)	765	2.5	.1521	.2788	1.833

Table 3. Simulation #3 (LOGICA E26-HIP-00166, Table 3.2.2.1, p.189)

B	N(B)	σ_0	σ_α	σ_α^T	Δ
5	72	.574	2.24	2.93	-24%
6	106	.840	2.38	3.00	-21
7	108	1.07	2.62	3.08	-15
8	110	1.48	2.70	3.26	-17
9	100	1.81	2.93	3.44	-15
10	112	2.38	3.35	3.81	-12
11	92	3.20	4.16	4.42	-6
12	100	4.62	5.27	5.64	-7

N = 800 $\bar{\Delta} = -14\%$

Table 4. Simulation #4 (LOGICA E26-HIP-00166, Table 3.2.2.2, p.190)

B	N(B)	σ_0	σ_α	σ_α^T	Δ
5	8	.449	3.43	2.88	+19%
6	20	.692	2.56	2.93	-13
7	81	1.02	2.90	3.03	-4
8	230	1.36	3.19	3.18	0
9	221	1.79	3.35	3.40	-2
10	116	2.36	3.84	3.77	+2
11	75	3.29	4.45	4.47	0
12	27	4.71	5.59	5.70	-2
13	7	6.54	6.74	7.43	-9

N = 785 $\bar{\Delta} = -1\%$

Table 5. Simulation #5 (LOGICA E26-HIP-00166, Table 3.2.2.3, p.191)

B	N(B)	σ_0	σ_α	σ_α^T	Δ
5	8	.324	2.75	2.78	-1%
6	20	.584	2.51	2.83	-11
7	81	.870	2.68	2.91	-8
8	230	1.26	2.91	3.06	-5
9	221	1.78	3.22	3.33	-3
10	116	2.35	3.66	3.70	-1
11	75	3.42	4.64	4.53	+2
12	27	5.08	6.04	6.01	+1
13	7	6.95	7.98	7.80	+2

N = 785 $\bar{\Delta} = -3\%$

Table 6. Simulation #6 (MATRA E21-HIP-00767, Fig. 3.2.4/1, p. 125)

B	N(B)	σ_0	σ_α	σ_α^T	Δ
5	8	.524	3.11	3.63	-14%
6	20	.652	2.76	3.65	-24
7	81	1.20	3.32	3.80	-13
8	230	1.58	3.39	3.95	-14
9	221	2.13	3.61	4.23	-15
10	116	3.29	4.65	4.98	-7
11	75	4.53	5.66	5.96	-5
12	27	7.86	7.21	9.00	-20
13	7	8.69	9.16	9.80	-7

N = 785 $\bar{\Delta} = -13\%$

Table 7. Simulation #7 (MATRA E21-HIP-00767, 'Basic Accuracy', pp. 180, 192)
 Note: σ_α is computed from $\sigma_\alpha^2 = \sigma_0^2 + (370 \text{ mas}^2)/14.88$

B	N(B)	σ_0	σ_α	σ_α^T	Δ
5.5	23	1.10	5.11	4.81	+6%
6.5	42	1.29	5.16	4.86	+6
7.5	116	1.75	5.29	5.02	+5
8.5	321	2.43	5.55	5.32	+4
9.5	126	3.28	5.97	5.80	+3
10.5	94	5.00	7.06	7.02	+1
11.5	47	7.24	8.79	8.91	-1
12.5	16	15.3	16.1	16.7	-4
N = 785				$\bar{\Delta} = +3\%$	

Table 8. Simulation #9 (Copenhagen GI set M-4; NDAC/LO/017 p. 7ff)

B	N(B)	σ_0	σ_α	σ_α^T	Δ
5.3	105	.575	1.30	1.28	+1%
6.6	227	.626	1.34	1.35	+2
7.6	628	.683	1.35	1.34	+1
8.4	1245	.784	1.45	1.40	+3
N = 2205				$\bar{\Delta} = +2\%$	

Table 9. Simulation #10 (Copenhagen GI set M-11; Lindegren 1983 March 28)

B	N(B)	σ_0	σ_α	σ_α^T	Δ
5.5	62	.499	2.99	2.87	+4%
6.5	105	.755	2.48	2.91	-15
7.5	275	1.08	2.10	3.04	-31
8.5	887	1.51	3.40	3.24	+5
9.5	342	2.12	3.64	3.60	+1
10.5	274	2.97	5.01	4.21	+19
11.5	127	4.31	5.42	5.33	+2
12.5	35	6.35	8.51	7.24	+18
N = 2107				$\bar{\Delta} = 0\%$	

For #1, 2, and 8 (fixed B), Table 2 gives

N = total number of stars per run

m = average number of stars per frame or FOV

σ_0 = $\sigma_\eta/\sqrt{n}$ ($= \sigma_{\text{PAN}}$ in the LOGICA report), with σ_η = rms measurement error and $n = M/N$ = average number of measurements per star

σ_α = rms abscissa error

H = σ_α/σ_0

For the remaining simulations, Tables 3 - 9 give, as functions of magnitude (B),

$N(B)$ = number of stars in magnitude interval $B \pm 0.5$ (usually)

σ_0 = $\sigma_\eta(B)/\sqrt{n}$

σ_α = $\sigma_\alpha(B)$

σ_α^T = fitted rms abscissa error from Eqn (32)

Δ = relative error of fit = $(\sigma_\alpha - \sigma_\alpha^T)/\sigma_\alpha^T$

The bottom line of each table gives the total number of stars and the average relative error of the fit [weighted by $N(B)$].

For the three simulations with fixed B (and therefore constant σ_0 and nearly constant σ_α), the 'slackness'

$$H = \langle \sigma_\alpha \rangle / \langle \sigma_0 \rangle \quad (20)$$

is practically independent of which kind of average is used (arithmetic, harmonic, ...) and thus defines the input/output relation without ambiguity. For the other simulations, in which σ_0 typically spans more than an order of magnitude, I define more generally

$$H_q = \langle \sigma_\alpha \rangle_q / \langle \sigma_0 \rangle_q \quad (21)$$

where the q-average is defined by

$$\langle x \rangle_q := \left[K^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^K (x_k)^q \right]^{1/q} \quad (22)$$

for any $q \neq 0$ and set of positive numbers x_k , $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$. It can be noted that

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 0} \langle x \rangle_q = \exp \left[K^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^K \ln(x_k) \right] \quad (23)$$

so that $\langle x \rangle_0$ is identified as the geometric mean. $q = 1$ and -1 give the arithmetic and harmonic mean, respectively. By convention, $\langle \rangle \equiv \langle \rangle_1$.

Table 10 gives H_q for the ten simulations and q between -2 and $+2$ (values for non-integer q are actually interpolated); Fig. 1 is a plot of the same data.

Table 10. $H_q = \langle \sigma_\alpha \rangle_q / \langle \sigma_0 \rangle_q$ versus q for the ten simulations

$q =$	-2	-1.5	-1	-0.5	0	0.5	1	1.5	2
#1	1.90	1.90	1.90	1.90	1.90	1.90	1.90	1.90	1.90
#2	1.93	1.93	1.93	1.93	1.93	1.93	1.93	1.93	1.93
#3	2.47	2.32	2.16	2.01	1.85	1.72	1.59	1.50	1.41
#4	2.37	2.27	2.18	2.09	2.01	1.93	1.84	1.76	1.68
#5	2.51	2.37	2.22	2.11	1.99	1.90	1.80	1.71	1.62
#6	2.27	2.15	2.03	1.93	1.83	1.72	1.62	1.52	1.42
#7	2.58	2.48	2.38	2.27	2.16	2.04	1.91	1.76	1.61
#8	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83
#9	1.95	1.94	1.94	1.93	1.93	1.93	1.92	1.92	1.91
#10	2.40	2.31	2.22	2.13	2.05	1.97	1.89	1.81	1.74

It is seen that most of the curves intersect near $q = 1$, i.e. that H_1 is relatively insensitive to the assumed distribution of σ_0 . This was also the conclusion in NDAC/LO/017 from small-scale GCRs with a wide variety of distributions. Exceptions are #3 and 6, for which H_1 is distinctly smaller than average. Simulation #3 uses a flat magnitude distribution from $B = 5$ to 12, and is therefore rather extreme; but #6 has a distribution very similar to several of the others, and I have no idea why it deviates so much. In the following I simply disregard #3 and 6.

FIGURE 1. H_q versus q for simulations #1 to 10

For the remaining eight simulations we have the following averages:

#1, 2, 4, 5, 7	(LOGICA/MATRA)	$H_1 = 1.88$	$\begin{matrix} +.05 \\ -.08 \end{matrix}$	(peak errors)
#9, 10	(Copenhagen GI)	$H_1 = 1.91$	$\begin{matrix} +.01 \\ -.02 \end{matrix}$	(peak errors)
#8	(Lindegren 1977)	$H_1 = 1.83$		(uncertain)

Thus it appears that independent GCR simulations at three different places agree to within a few per cent, and that

$$H_1 = 1.90 \pm 0.05 \quad (\text{peak error}) \quad (24)$$

is a fair and even slightly conservative estimate of the overall GCR accuracy.

4. Comparison of simulation results: Accuracy versus magnitude

The results of the previous section permit to estimate the average abscissa rms error ($\langle \sigma_\alpha \rangle = \langle \sigma_\alpha \rangle_1$) once the distribution of σ_η or σ_0 versus magnitude is known:

$$\langle \sigma_\alpha \rangle_1 = H_1 \langle \sigma_0 \rangle_1 = H_1 \frac{1}{N} \sum_B N(B) \sigma_0(B) = H_1 \frac{1}{N} \sum_B N(B) \sigma_\eta(B) / \sqrt{n} \quad (25)$$

I will now discuss how to extend this to estimating the rms abscissa error as function of magnitude, $\sigma_\alpha(B)$.

Two different functional types relating $\sigma_\alpha(B)$ to $\sigma_0(B)$ and $N(B)$ have been proposed. The SDR formula and variants discussed by MATRA/LOGICA are of the quadratic type

$$\sigma_\alpha^2(B) = b \langle \sigma_0 \rangle_q^2 + c \sigma_0^2(B) \quad (26)$$

while in NDAC/LO/017 I proposed the linear type

$$\sigma_{\alpha}(B) = H(1-h) \langle \sigma_0 \rangle_q + Hh \sigma_0(B) \quad (27)$$

with $q = 1$. If we want to represent a given set of GCR values $\sigma_{\alpha}(B)$, $\sigma_0(B)$ by (26) or (27), we clearly must fit a hyperbola or a straight line, respectively, through the points. When $\sigma_0(B)$ spans a relatively narrow interval (as is the case with M-4 analysed in NDAC/LO/017), both forms may fit the points equally well; but if the fitted relations are extrapolated in either direction, the linear form (27) invariably falls below (26) and may even predict negative rms errors! For that reason I now reject (27) even though, empirically, it almost fits the simulation results better than the quadratic type (cf. Fig. 4).

With $c = 1$, Eqn (26) has a simple physical interpretation pointed out by MATRA/LOGICA. The first term represents the attitude variance, i.e. the average variance of the frame attitude (ω) divided by the number of frames in which the star is observed, while the second term represents the variance contributed by the measurement errors on the star itself with respect to the frame attitudes. LOGICA in fact refer to σ_0^2 as the abscissa variance with perfect attitude knowledge (σ_{PAN}^2). This interpretation is supported by the experiments by Lindegren and Söderhjelm (1980 Dec 2) which indicated $c = 1$.

Still I must caution against assuming strictly $c = 1$ only from this argument. If we consider a specific star, for which the abscissa is to be calculated, we must use only the other stars in each frame to determine the frame attitudes. Then, if the star is dim, less time than average is available for the other stars and the frame attitude variance is consequently higher than average. From this it appears that the effective attitude variance, relevant to a given star, will not be constant but slightly increasing with the magnitude of the star. I will not attempt to modelize this effect quantitatively, but it is reasonable to assume that it will lead to a value for c in (26) slightly greater than unity.

Table 11 lists the empirical values of $b \langle \sigma_0 \rangle_q^2$ and c in (26) obtained by least-squares fits to the seven simulations with a spread in magnitude. Rms uncertainties were estimated by assigning standard deviations to the abscissa variances in Tables 3-10 (excepting #7) according to

Table 11. Least-squares estimates of the parameters in (26) from fits to simulation results, with estimated rms uncertainties.

Simulation	Unconstrained fit		Constrained, $c = 1.10$
	$b\langle\sigma_0\rangle_q^2$	c	$b\langle\sigma_0\rangle_q^2$
#3	4.50 ± 0.23	1.12 ± 0.08	4.62 ± 0.19
#4	7.90 ± 0.43	1.10 ± 0.10	7.90 ± 0.29
#5	6.42 ± 0.34	1.25 ± 0.10	6.77 ± 0.24
#6	8.93 ± 0.47	1.02 ± 0.09	8.62 ± 0.35
#9	1.13 ± 0.32	1.57 ± 0.59	1.37 ± 0.06
#10	5.81 ± 0.44	1.80 ± 0.14	7.30 ± 0.32

$$\text{s.d.}[\sigma_\alpha^2(B)] \simeq K^{-\frac{1}{2}} [2/N(B)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \overline{\sigma_\alpha^2(B)} \quad (28)$$

where K is the number of GCR runs in the simulation, for which the results have been averaged, and $\overline{\sigma_\alpha^2(B)}$ is a smoothed variance computed from a preliminary graphical fit. $K = 1$ for the Copenhagen simulations (#9, 10), while I assumed $K = 4$ for the LOGICA/MATRA simulations.

Most of the simulations are compatible with a c -value slightly above one, say $c = 1.1$. Simulation #9 (Copenhagen M-4) gives a very poor determination of c due to the small spread of σ_0 values. Only #10 (Copenhagen M-11) seems to give a significantly higher c -value. The data points for that simulation are plotted in Fig. 2 together with error bars (± 1 s.d.) from (28) and two least-squares fit: the solid curve is the unconstrained fit with $c = 1.80$, the dashed curve is a fit with c constrained to 1.1. It is evident that the points scatter much more than expected from the formal standard deviations, so that the fit is rather poor also with the high value of c . This latter is apparently due mainly to the two points near $\sigma_0 = 1.1$ and 3.0, while the rightmost two points are fairly consistent with $c = 1.1$. On the whole, I do not think M-11 can be taken as serious evidence for a higher c -value.

Adopting $c = 1.10$, the last column of Table 11 gives the constrained least-squares values of the first term in (26).

FIGURE 2. Rms abscissa error versus $\sigma_\alpha(B)/\sqrt{n}$ for #10 = Copenhagen GI M-11

I now turn to the determination of q in (26), i.e. which kind of average should be used for calculating the effective 'attitude variance'. In the SDR formula (5), we have $q = 2$. On the other hand MATRA argue, on theoretical grounds, in favour of a harmonic mean of the variances ($q = -2$). In analogy with the analysis in Section 3 I will take the pragmatic view that q should be such as to minimize the variation of the numerical factor b between different simulations. That is, q is chosen to make the GCR formula almost insensitive to the distribution of σ_0 . Figure 3 is a plot of

$$b^{\frac{1}{2}}(q) = \langle \sigma_0 \rangle^{-1} \left[b \langle \sigma_0 \rangle^{\frac{2}{q}} \right]_{c=1.10}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (29)$$

versus q for the ten simulations. See also Table 12.

Table 12. $b^{\frac{1}{2}}$ as function of q for the ten simulations (assuming $c = 1.10$)

$q =$	-2	-1.5	-1	-0.5	0	0.5	1	1.5	2
#1	1.59	1.59	1.59	1.59	1.59	1.59	1.59	1.59	1.59
#2	1.62	1.62	1.62	1.62	1.62	1.62	1.62	1.62	1.62
#3	1.82	1.69	1.56	1.42	1.29	1.18	1.07	0.99	0.91
#4	1.96	1.87	1.78	1.70	1.62	1.55	1.47	1.40	1.32
#5	2.05	1.91	1.78	1.67	1.57	1.47	1.38	1.29	1.20
#6	1.78	1.67	1.57	1.47	1.38	1.28	1.19	1.10	1.01
#7	2.17	2.08	1.98	1.88	1.77	1.65	1.52	1.38	1.24
#8	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50
#9	1.63	1.62	1.62	1.62	1.61	1.61	1.61	1.60	1.60
#10	2.02	1.90	1.79	1.69	1.59	1.50	1.41	1.32	1.23

As in Fig. 1 it turns out that #3 and 6 are abnormally low; otherwise the curves intersect near $q = 0.5$. Disregarding these two simulations, we have the following averages:

#1, 2, 4, 5, 7	(LOGICA/MATRA)	$b^{\frac{1}{2}}(q = 0.5) = 1.58 \begin{matrix} +.07 \\ -.11 \end{matrix}$ (peak errors)
#9, 10	(Copenhagen GI)	$b^{\frac{1}{2}}(q = 0.5) = 1.56 \begin{matrix} +.05 \\ -.06 \end{matrix}$ (peak errors)
#8	(Lindegren 1977)	$b^{\frac{1}{2}}(q = 0.5) = 1.50$ (uncertain)

FIGURE 3. $b^{1/2}$ versus q for simulations #1 to 10

from which I deduce

$$b^{\frac{1}{2}}(0.5) = 1.57 \pm 0.10 \quad (\text{peak error}) \quad (30)$$

(with a slightly conservative error estimate).

For $c = 1.10$, a peak error of ± 0.10 is reasonable in view of Table 11 and considering that we must have $c \geq 1$. Thus

$$c^{\frac{1}{2}} = 1.05 \pm 0.05 \quad (\text{peak error}) \quad (31)$$

which in combination with (30) gives the quadratic GCR formula

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^2(B) = \left[(1.57 \pm .10) \langle \sigma_0 \rangle_{0.5} \right]^2 + \left[(1.05 \pm .05) \sigma_0(B) \right]^2 \quad (\text{peak errors}) \quad (32)$$

This relation is shown in Fig. 4 (solid curve) together with the data points for simulations #1 to 10 (except #7). In order to plot all the points in a single diagram, they have been normalized to $\langle \sigma_0 \rangle_{0.5}$ of respective simulation.

[That $q \approx 0.5$ is the proper average in (26) can be derived analytically from the result that H_1 is nearly independent of the σ_0 -distribution. For if σ_0 is modelled as a stochastic variable with mean $\langle \sigma_0 \rangle$ and variance $s^2 \langle \sigma_0 \rangle^2$, we have (for small s^2)

$$\langle \sigma_0 \rangle_q = \left[1 + \frac{1}{2}(q-1)s^2 + \dots \right] \langle \sigma_0 \rangle \quad (33)$$

and

$$\langle \sigma_{\alpha} \rangle = E \left[(b \langle \sigma_0 \rangle_q^2 + c \sigma_0^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] = (b+c)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[1 + \frac{(q-1)b+c}{2(b+c)} s^2 + \dots \right] \langle \sigma_0 \rangle \quad (34)$$

Then, if

$$q = 1 - (c/b) \quad (35)$$

it is seen that

FIGURE 4. Normalized abscissa error versus normalized $\sigma_0(B)$.

Solid curve: relation (32) (with constants 1.57 and 1.05)

Dashed curve: SDR relation for typical distribution of $\sigma_0(B)$

Symbols:

- | | | | | | |
|-----------|-------|-------------------|------------------|-----|---------------------|
| Δ | #1, 2 | (LOGICA, fixed B) | + | #6 | (MATRA) |
| x | #3 | (LOGICA) | ∇ | #8 | (Lindgren, fixed B) |
| o | #4 | (LOGICA) | $\blacktriangle$ | #9 | (GI, M-4) |
| $\square$ | #5 | (LOGICA) | $\bullet$ | #10 | (GI, M-11) |

$$H_1 \equiv \langle \sigma_\alpha \rangle / \langle \sigma_0 \rangle \approx (b+c)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (36)$$

independent of s^2 to first order. By means of (36), condition (35) can also be written

$$q = 1 - c/(H_1^2 - c) \quad (37)$$

or $q \approx 0.56$ for $H_1 = 1.9$, $c = 1.1$.]

5. Discussion of the SDR formula and MATRA's 'Basic Accuracy'

Accepting H_1 as a suitable measure of the GCR accuracy (being rather insensitive to the magnitude distribution), we have in Table 13 a direct comparison of simulation results with expected values according to the 'best fit' formula (32) and the SDR formula (5) or (19).

Table 13. Values of $H_1 \equiv \langle \sigma_\alpha \rangle / \langle \sigma_0 \rangle$ according to simulations (Table 10), the 'best fit' equation (32), and the SDR formula (19). Simulation #7.1 is a hypothetical variant of #7 with twice as many $B = 12.5$ stars (see text).

Simulation #	1*	2*	3	4	5	6	7	7.1	8*	9	10
experimental H_1	= 1.90	1.93	1.59	1.84	1.80	1.62	1.91	----	1.83	1.92	1.89
best fit (32) H_1	= 1.89	1.89	1.84	1.86	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.84	1.89	1.88	1.85
SDR formula H_1	= 2.00	2.00	2.31	2.20	2.25	2.31	2.38	2.49	2.00	2.01	2.24

* constant σ_0 (fixed B)

For fixed B (#1, 2, 8) the SDR formula gives a very reasonable $H_1 = 2.00$. This is consistent with points A and B in Section 2, viz. that the formula is based on simulation #8 with a variance margin of 1.176: $1.83 \times \sqrt{1.176} = 1.98$. For realistic distributions of σ_0 , the SDR formula however becomes much more conservative, increasing the margin to about 1.5 on the abscissa variance. This is clearly due to the combination of ill-founded assumptions under points C and D in Section 2, which in the first place puts too much emphasis on the constant term in (15), and then lets it increase as $\langle \sigma_0^2 \rangle$ rather than $\langle \sigma_0 \rangle^2$, thus making the formula unduly sensitive to σ_0 for the faintest stars.

The last point is perhaps more clearly demonstrated by considering what happens when the fraction of very faint stars is increased. In Table 13, #7.1 stands for a hypothetical case with twice as many $B = 12.5$ stars as in #7. Thus I have increased $N(12.5)$ from 16 to 32, and decreased $N(8.5)$ from 321 to 305, but otherwise retained $N(B)$ and $\sigma_0(B)$ as in Table 7. In the SDR formula, this increases $\langle \sigma_0^2 \rangle$ by 30%, while in (32), the corresponding factor $\langle \sigma_0 \rangle_{0.5}^2$ is increased only by 6%. According to our interpretation of the quadratic GCR formula, these numbers represent the deterioration of the effective attitude variance. It is however difficult to imagine that such small a modification of $N(B)$ will actually increase the attitude variance by as much as 30%. Indeed, these very faint stars hardly contribute at all to the frame attitude determination, which is rather expected to suffer indirectly only, from the reduced number of brighter stars (3% less with $B < 9$). The increase by 6% predicted by (32) then appears much more reasonable. The predicted effects on the rms abscissa error is an increase by 13% according to the SDR formula, and by 8% according to (32). Note that H_1 remains almost the same for the modified distribution according to (32), but would increase rather significantly according to SDR.

For realistic measurement error distributions, the SDR formula thus predicts average rms abscissa errors which are about 22% higher than according to simulations and my 'best fit' formula (32). The margin factor is however not independent of magnitude. In Fig. 4 I have marked by a dashed curve the SDR relation as resulting from the σ_0 distribution of #7. (Other distributions will give different curves in this diagram, increasing the margin the higher proportion of faint stars is included.) The margin with respect to (32) (solid curve) is about 33% for very bright stars and 18% for the faintest. A similar, slightly less magnitude dependent difference is obtained by Vaghi (ESA-HIP-01624, Table 2), comparing the rms abscissa errors according to the SDR formula and MATRA's 'Basic Accuracy'.

Vaghi also points out that the SDR formula without 'margin factor' 1.45 agrees rather well with the 'Basic Accuracy' estimates. As we have seen, the factor 1.45 is not really, historically speaking, a margin; that it is close to the average ratio between the SDR variance and the simulation results is pure coincidence.

He concludes that the controversy is mainly related to the interpretation of the 'attitude variance' term containing $\langle \sigma_\eta^2 \rangle$: in MATRA's view, the use of an arithmetic mean of the variances is exceedingly penalizing and

conceptually incorrect. As I hope to have demonstrated above, this is in fact a very valid criticism. However, MATRA/LOGICA also seem to argue that a harmonic mean of the variances should be used instead.

In practice, this argument mainly serves to discredit the SDR formula, but is not really tested against their own simulations. Consider for instance the 'tests of magnitude dependence' described in the LOGICA report (E26-HIP-00166) p. 188ff. At first a quadratic model

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^2(B) = \sigma_{att}^2 + \sigma_0^2(B) \quad (38)$$

is adopted. The attitude term is then expressed in terms of the harmonic mean variance as

$$\sigma_{att}^2 = (V-1) \langle \sigma_0 \rangle_{-2}^2 \quad (39)$$

with

$$V = N^{-1} \sum_B N(B) \sigma_{\alpha}^2(B) / \sigma_0^2(B) \quad (40)$$

Combining (39) and (40) gives

$$\sigma_{att}^2 = \frac{\sum_B N(B) \sigma_0^{-2}(B) [\sigma_{\alpha}^2(B) - \sigma_0^2(B)]}{\sum_B N(B) \sigma_0^{-2}(B)} \quad (41)$$

Calculating σ_{att}^2 from (39) - (40) is thus equivalent to least-squares fitting the model (38) while weighting each point by $N(B) \sigma_0^{-2}(B)$. If the model (38) is correct, any weighted mean of $\sigma_{\alpha}^2(B) - \sigma_0^2(B)$ is an unbiased estimate of σ_{att}^2 ; thus it appears that it is in reality only the model (38) which is tested, and not the use of a harmonic mean variance in (39). [The last column in LOGICA's Tables 3.2.2.1 - 3.2.2.3 is headed 'experimental/predicted' and might suggest to the casual reader that it is some version of the GCR formula that is tested, predicting the abscissa variances from the values $\sigma_0^2(B)$ in the first column. This is not the case; a more appropriate heading would be 'experimental/fit'.] Incidentally, if the fluctuations of simulated $\sigma_{\alpha}^2(B)$ are due to the limited sample sizes, the best weighting would be by

$N(B)[\overline{\sigma_\alpha^2}]^{-2}$, according to (28).

A real test of the predictive power of a harmonic mean in (39) would be to compare V from (40) with $H_2^2 = \langle \sigma_\alpha^2 \rangle / \langle \sigma_0^2 \rangle$, which according to the SDR formula is assumed to be constant and equal to $1.45 \times 2.77 = 4.0165$. If the simulations show that V is less sensitive than H_2^2 to the assumed magnitude distribution, then a harmonic mean of σ_0^2 is preferable to the arithmetic when it comes to predicting the abscissa variances without actually doing the GCR. Such a comparison is made in Table 14, and shows that V is indeed slightly less variable than H_2^2 ; however, as expected from the results of Section 3, H_1^2 is of course even better.

Table 14. Comparison of various measures of the GCR variance ratio

Simulation	$V = \langle \frac{\sigma_\alpha^2}{\sigma_0^2} \rangle$	$H_2^2 = \frac{\langle \sigma_\alpha^2 \rangle}{\langle \sigma_0^2 \rangle}$	$H_1^2 = \frac{\langle \sigma_\alpha \rangle^2}{\langle \sigma_0 \rangle^2}$
1	3.63	3.63	3.63
2	3.73	3.73	3.73
3	4.66	2.00	2.54
4	5.00	2.81	3.40
5	5.26	2.61	3.23
6	4.25	2.02	2.63
7	5.85	2.59	3.63
8	3.36	3.36	3.36
9	3.76	3.68	3.69
10	5.20	2.99	3.58
all simulations:	$4.47 \pm 19\%$	$2.84 \pm 21\%$	$3.34 \pm 13\%$
excluding #3, 6:	$4.47 \pm 21\%$	$3.05 \pm 15\%$	$3.53 \pm 5\%$

N.B.: percentages are relative rms dispersions

6. Conclusions

The theoretical analyses and numerical simulations done by LOGICA and MATRA have very significantly contributed to a better understanding of the GCR error propagation and have led to some well-founded criticism of the SDR approach. However, except to determine σ_{att}^2 directly from GCR simulations, MATRA have not proposed any real alternative to the SDR formula. Still, I think that the problem is now sufficiently understood, and the simulations sufficiently concordant, that a good alternative can be presented.

We have seen that the SDR formula was originally derived for random star positions but fixed magnitude, in which case it gives a very reasonable ratio $H_1 = 2.00$ between the average rms abscissa error and effective measurement error per star (σ_0). When extrapolating to a realistic magnitude distribution, however, some quite arbitrary prescription was followed, which is now known to be very conservative and without foundation either from theory or experiment.

On the other hand we have now an expression, (32), which reproduces the average rms error ratio of the different simulations to within $\pm 3\%$ (excepting simulations #3 and 6, which give smaller abscissa errors), and the magnitude dependence reasonably well and in a theoretically acceptable form. It is in particular worth noticing that the independent and formally quite different simulations by LOGICA/MATRA and the Geodetic Institute in Copenhagen give results in almost perfect agreement.

In view of all this, I propose that the current SDR formula (5) is replaced by one based on the 'best fit' formula (32), but with a suitable and explicit error margin. The peak errors quoted in (32) correspond to a maximum error on the abscissa variance of 13% for bright stars and 10% at the faint limit. I propose a uniform margin of 17% on the abscissa variance, corresponding to $H_1 = 2.00$ also for realistic magnitude distributions. Retaining assumption E of Section 2, which is reasonable and apparently uncontroversial, the complete GCR formula proposed is

$$\sigma_{\alpha i}^2 = 1.17 \left\{ (N/M)A^2 + 1.10 \left(\sum_{j \in i} \sigma_{\eta j}^{-2} \right)^{-1} \right\} \quad (42)$$

with

$$A = 1.57 \left(\frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \sigma_{\eta j}^{0.5} \right)^2 \quad (42a)$$

7. Addendum

After the preceding analysis was completed I received two Technical Notes with additional simulation results and discussions of the GCR formula: 'Accuracy Analysis Mid-Term Report' by Zeis (MAT-HIP-4893) and 'LOGICA Mid-Term Accuracy Simulation Report' by Burrows and Davies (LOG-HIP-04918). A cursory analysis of the new material indicates excellent agreement with the 'best fit' formula (32); see Fig. 5. Table 15 below shows that the slackness parameter is consistently about 10% below the value $H_1 = 2.00$ corresponding to the proposed new formula.

It is also interesting that LOGICA note (p. 37) some deviations from (38) at extreme magnitudes, which they explain as a slight magnitude dependence of σ_{att}^2 due to precisely the effect which motivated $c > 1$ in Section 4. The new material seems to support the adopted value $c = 1.1$.

Table 15. Values of H_1 for the new simulations

Reference	H_1
MAT-HIP-4893, Fig. 16 (p. 39)	1.80
LOG-HIP-4918, Table 11	1.84
"- , Table 12	1.82
"- , Table 13	1.81
"- , Table 14	1.82
"- , Table 15	1.86

FIGURE 5. Normalized abscissa rms error versus normalized (B)

Curve: relation (32)

- Symbols:
- Δ MAT-HIP-4893, Fig. 16 (785 stars randomly distributed)
 - $\circ$ LOG-HIP-4918, Table 11 (nominal weights, frame errors only)
 - $+$ " " , Table 14 (do. + chromaticity)
 - $\bullet$ " " , Table 15 (occultations and basic angle variations)

Estimation of the variance V in (A2.1)

Lindegren 77-04-15

The variance V in eq. (A2.1) couples the mean error of a measurement of the distance between two stars in the grid system to the "mean error per orbit" of a star's position along the reference great circle. In Hög's note 11 it was estimated by an analogy to the determination of division corrections. For a density $\rho = 1$ star deg^{-2} and field width $w = 1^\circ$ we get $V = 0.50$ ($m = 3$) or $V = 0.30$ ($m = 4$). $m-1$ is the average number of stars to which a particular star is tied by direct measurements of distances in the grid system (each measurement being counted once only, i.e. from star 1 to star 2 but not from star 2 to star 1). m depends on the length of the field of view.

The main objection to this method is that the actual (random) distribution of stars in both coordinates is not taken into account. Furthermore, the pole of the scan moves continuously during observations and in order to determine all instrumental constants we have to consider more than one orbit at a time.

More precise estimates of V have been obtained from numerical experiments carried out as follows. The parameters determining the problem are:

- ρ = density of stars (deg^{-2})
- w, l = width and length of either field of view (deg)
- γ = basic angle (deg)
- n_0 = number of consecutive orbits considered in one solution
- ω = speed at which the axis of rotation changes direction
(deg/orbit)

The procedure is straight-forward. Random stellar positions with the given average density are generated and "scanned" by the two fields. Every possible connexion (two stars in the complex field at the same time) is recorded and the equation of condition (A1.1, page 4) is formulated. However, the left member (the O-C) is replaced by a random gaussian number with unit variance. All p-f connexions were recorded in this way but in the frequent case when two stars might be connected both p-p and f-f, only one of them (chosen at random) was recorded. After all "observations" have been made, a check is made that every star is (directly or indirectly) connected to all other stars, and that the chain of connexions make up a closed circle.

The normal equations are formed and the equation $\sum_i dv_i = 0$ and the corresponding Lagrangean multiplier added. The equations are solved according to the method of conjugate gradients (see below). The unknowns which are determined are dv_i for each star, and six instrumental constants (basic angle correction, scale value, zero-point perpendicular to the scan, and three angles for the orientation and tilt of the grid). We then have

$$V = p \cdot \langle dv_i^2 \rangle$$

where p is the average number of orbits in this group during which a star is observed:

$$p = (N, \text{ total number of stars in the group}) / (360^\circ \cdot w \cdot \varphi).$$

Table 1 shows some results of the experiments. n_c is the number of connexions or angle measurements, $t = 0.8 \cdot 95^m n_o / n_c$ is the average time available for each angle measurement. $(V/t)^{0.5}$ is the mean error of dv_i in terms of the mean error of an angle measurement obtained with 1^s integration time.

Table 1. Result of numerical simulations of step 1.

Constant parameters: $\varphi = 1 \text{ star deg}^{-2}$, $n_o = 8$, $\omega = 0.28 \text{ /orbit}$.

γ	w	l	N	n_c	$\langle dv_i^2 \rangle$	p	V	t	$(V/t)^{0.5}$
60°	0.9°	1.2°	765	7904	0.285	2.36	0.672	4.62	0.381
63	0.9	1.2	765	7834	0.0829	2.36	0.196	4.66	0.205
64	0.9	1.2	765	7879	0.0813	2.36	0.192	4.63	0.204
63	0.9	1.4	765	9097	0.0690	2.36	0.163	4.01	0.202

- Conclusions:
1. $\gamma = 60^\circ$ is unfavourable, as predicted by the simplified analysis (Høg's note 11)
 2. A longer field decreases V but this is compensated by the shorter time available for each connexion.
 3. $V = 0.20$ rather than 0.5 used in the MDS.